

ON THE STUDY OF SOME MONOFLOPHOSPHATES AND THEIR ANALOGY AND ISOMORPHISM WITH SULPHATES*.

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The work of Sarkar and Ray (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 987) on the homology of the fluo-beryllates and sulphates led to enquire whether other radicals can be found analogous to sulphates. From the table of ionic radii given by Goldschmidt (*Trans. Faraday, Soc.*, 1919, 25, 282) it follows that compounds of PO_3F ion, if possible to isolate should behave exactly like similar compounds of SO_4 ions (pentavalent positively charged phosphorous ion having the same ionic radius as that of hexavalent positively charged sulphur ion— $0.34\text{\AA}$ —and the negatively charged fluorine and oxygen ions having approximately equal ionic radii— $1.33\text{\AA}$ and $1.32\text{\AA}$ respectively).

These two ions are isosteric and isoelectric being both bivalent and having thirty two peripheric electrons.

A search in the literature shows that Dorfust and Balz (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, 187, 197) have found that all simple and complex salts of fluoroborates and perchlorates are perfectly isomorphous. The respective solubilities of these salts are also very close and even the organic salts of these acids are physically and chemically similar. Weinland and Alpha (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1899, 21, 43) prepared potassium, rubidium and caesium monofluophosphates of the formula, $\text{R}'\text{O}'\text{P}(\text{OH})_3\text{F}$, by evaporating a mixture of tertiary phosphates and hydroxides in molecular proportions, dissolved in concentrated hydrofluoric acid. According to Werner they are not to be regarded as true fluo-phosphates (fluorine replacing oxygen), but additive compounds of hydrofluoric acid and ortho-phosphates having the formula $\text{R}'\text{H}_2\text{PO}_3\text{HF}$, where R represents potassium, rubidium or caesium.

Lange (*Ber.*, 1927, 60, 965; 1928, 61, 729) observed that POF_3 hydrolyses, unlike POCl_3 , in stages probably according to the scheme,

and prepared the ammonium salt, $\text{NH}_4\text{PO}_3\text{F}_2$ corresponding to the first stage acid HPO_2F_2 which showed close analogy with the perchlorates.

* The present work was undertaken in the early part of 1929 and was submitted as a thesis for the M. Sc. Examination in 1930.

The starting material potassium difluophosphate was prepared according to Lange's method (*loc. cit.*). It was then hydrolysed with dilute KOH on the water-bath in the proportion of one molecule of potassium salt to two molecules of the alkali. In order to isolate the expected second hydrolytic product K_2PO_3F , the solution was evaporated in vacuum over sulphuric acid till the salts began to crystallise out. A suspended crystal of potassium sulphate was found to grow uniformly in the filtered solution suggesting that an isomorphous fluophosphate ion has been formed in the solution. The isolation of the fluophosphate by this method is rather tedious and takes a very long time. A second method of isolation of the monofluophosphate was tried directly from phosphoric anhydride and hydrofluoric acid (40 %). The two acids were mixed and neutralised with caustic soda in the cold and the excess of phosphoric acid was then removed by addition of silver nitrate. The monofluophosphate was precipitated by excess of silver nitrate but the yield was very small.

During the progress of the present work there appeared a paper from Lange (*Ber.*, 1929, 62, 763) in which he described a method for the isolation of ammonium monofluophosphate from ammonium fluoride and phosphorous pentoxide. The other two methods (already tried by us independently) were also anticipated by Lange (*Ber.*, 1929, 62B, 1084; 1931, 64B, 2772) who made a detailed study of equilibrium between phosphoric acid and water. However, in course of the present work, Lange's method of preparing ammonium fluophosphate was taken advantage of, the molecular volume of K_2PO_3F being very close to that of K_2SO_4 , the isomorphism of the sulphate and fluophosphate ions was taken as the criterion of chemical analogy and we prepared copper monofluophosphate analogous to $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$, that of nickel to $NiSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, of cobalt to $CoSO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$, etc. Besides the double salts of ammonium monofluophosphate and the monofluophosphates of the bivalent metals, viz., Ni, Co etc., have been isolated in monoclinic crystals, perfectly isomorphous with the corresponding double sulphates of Locke (*Amer. J. Sci.*, 1902, 27, 455). The double salts of aluminium monofluophosphate and ammonium monofluophosphate have been prepared and found perfectly isomorphous with the corresponding alum. Mixed crystals of the type, $NiSO_4(NH_4)_2PO_3F \cdot 6H_2O$ and $RSO_4(NH_4)_2PO_3F \cdot 6H_2O$ where R represents Co, Cu, Zn, Mn, etc., have also been prepared.

It has been further found that the double salt of ammonium fluoberyllate and nickel fluoberyllate forms mixed crystals and grows uniformly in a saturated solution of the corresponding double salt of the monofluophosphates.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Nickel Monofluophosphate.—Pure nickel chloride was dissolved in the least quantity of water and cooled in ice. An equimolecular quantity of silver monofluophosphate prepared according to Lange (*loc. cit.*) was made into a thin cream with water and run slowly into the nickel chloride solution with constant stirring. Double decomposition took place with the separation of silver chloride which was filtered and the filtrate was tested for Ag and Cl ions, the excess of one or the other ion being removed by careful addition of a very dilute solution of either nickel chloride or silver monofluophosphate, as the case might be. It was filtered and allowed to crystallise in vacuum over sulphuric acid. The crystals appeared in 2-3 days. (Found : Ni, 20·82; P, 10·98; H₂O, 44·60. NiPO₃F, 7H₂O requires Ni, 20·73; P, 11·0; H₂O, 44·60 per cent).

Cobalt monofluophosphate was prepared exactly in the same way as the previous nickel salt. (Found : Co, 22·24; P, 11·09; H₂O, 40·48. CoPO₃F, 6H₂O requires Co, 22·23; P, 11·69; H₂O, 40·76 per cent).

Copper monofluophosphate was prepared in a similar way to that of nickel. The copper salt is very difficult to crystallise. At first basic copper fluoride separates out which is removed from time to time by filtration and finally a few crystals are obtained.

It was more conveniently prepared in a fine condition by the addition of alcohol to the ice-cold solution of copper monofluophosphate. (Found : Cu, 25·09; P, 12·34; H₂O, 35·80. CuPO₃F, 5H₂O requires Cu, 25·25; P, 12·35; H₂O, 35·85 per cent).

Zinc monofluophosphate was prepared in solution in a similar way to that of the nickel salt, and was crystallised with equal difficulty. The crystallisation was only effected by cautiously adding absolute alcohol to the zinc monofluophosphate solution which was cooled in ice. The solution was stirred all along and fine crystals were obtained which was filtered and dried in vacuum. Kuhn (*Schweigger's J.*, 1830, 60, 337) and Hannay (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1877, 32, 382) prepared an analogous pentahydrated zinc sulphate. (Found : Zn, 25·65; P, 12·24; H₂O, 35·39. ZnPO₃F, 5H₂O requires Zn, 25·69; P, 12·26; H₂O, 35·57 per cent).

Other hydrate of the zinc compound could not be obtained.

Preparation of the Double Salt of Nickel and Ammonium Monofluophosphate.

Nickel monofluophosphate and ammonium monofluophosphate were taken in equimolecular proportion and dissolved in the least quantity of

water and allowed to crystallise under low vacuum over fused calcium chloride.

The crystals were obtained in a few days and were dried under folds of blotting paper and analysed. In the mother liquor crystals of nickel ammonium sulphate grows uniformly. [Found : Ni, 14.54 ; P, 15.25 ; F, 9.0. $\text{NiPO}_3\text{F}(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{PO}_3\text{F}, 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 14.57 ; P, 15.55 ; F, 9.55 per cent].

The hexahydrated crystals are unstable at the ordinary temperature. It loses four out of its six molecules of water of crystallisation and falls into a fine powder. The dehydrated salt is very stable and retains the two molecules of water of crystallisation even at 100°.

Cobalt Ammonium Monofluophosphate.—Equimolecular quantities of cobalt monofluophosphate and ammonium monofluophosphate were dissolved in the least quantity of water and crystallised. [Found : Co, 14.80 ; P, 15.52. $\text{CoPO}_3\text{F}(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{PO}_3\text{F}, 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 14.79 ; P, 15.53 per cent).

The hexahydrated crystals are unstable and loses four molecules of water of crystallisation. The double salt of ammonium monofluophosphate and copper, manganese, zinc, and magnesium fluophosphate could not be obtained.

Preparation of the Alum.

Aluminium Ammonium Monofluophosphate.—An equivalent quantity of silver monofluophosphate was added with stirring to an ice-cooled solution of a weighed quantity of aluminium chloride. The solution was filtered and to the filtrate an equimolecular quantity of ammonium monofluophosphate was added, and it was allowed to crystallise under low vacuum over sulphuric acid. The solution turned turbid with the separation of AlF_3 , which was filtered off. This was continued for a few days, after which the hydrolysis stopped. Before the solution turned syrupy it was placed in open air. The crystallisation takes a long time. [Found : Al, 5.90 ; P, 13.49. $\text{Al}_2(\text{PO}_3\text{F})_2(\text{Am})_2\text{PO}_3\text{F}, 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires, Al, 5.91 ; P, 13.57 per cent].

The Double Salt of Nickel Sulphate and Ammonium Monofluophosphate.—Heptahydrated nickel sulphate and recrystallised ammonium monofluophosphate were taken in the molecular proportion (1 : 1) and dissolved in the least quantity of water and allowed to crystallise under low vacuum over calcium chloride. In a day or two crystals began to appear which were removed and the mother liquor was placed in a glass chamber.

A large number of crystals were obtained which was analysed and the following results were obtained. The percentage of SO_4 was higher and that of P was proportionately lower than the percentage required by the true double salt.

	Ni.	P.	SO_4 .
Percentage	14.82	4.123	37.97
Atomic ratio	0.2525	0.133	0.395

Ratio of the metal : ratio of the acid = 1 : 2.09. Hence the formula of the compound may be written as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Ni}(\text{PO}_3\text{F}, \text{SO}_4)_2, 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

From the mother liquor a second set of crystals was obtained in another two days and on analysis it was found to contain 32.74% SO_4 . The percentage of SO_4 in the second set of crystals was lower than the first set. It was then thought that it would be possible to isolate the true double salt having the formula $\text{NiSO}_4(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{PO}_3\text{F}, 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by successive fractional crystallisation.

In the third set of crystal the percentage of SO_4 was still lower and the fourth set of crystal was found to contain 24.04% of SO_4 which in accordance with the formula $\text{NiSO}_4(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{PO}_3\text{F}, 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires 24.24% of SO_4 .

At this stage the mother liquor was analysed and the ratio of the nickel sulphate and ammonium monofluophosphate was found to be as 1 : 3. It is thus found that the double salt is only stable with excess of PO_3F ions.

Preparation of the Mixed Crystals of Cobalt Sulphate and Ammonium Monofluophosphate.—Pure cobalt sulphate and recrystallised ammonium monofluophosphate were weighed out in the molecular proportion (1 : 1) and dissolved in the least quantity of water and allowed to crystallise under low vacuum over a few lumps of calcium chloride. Crystals were obtained in the form of crusts.

	Percentage.	Atomic ratio.
Co	14.79	0.2506
SO_4	26.47	0.2756
P	6.825	0.2202

Ratio of the metal : ratio of the acid = 0.2506 : 0.4956 = 1 : 1.98
Hence the formula may be written as $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_4)_2(\text{SO}_4, \text{PO}_3\text{F})_2, 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Preparation of the Mixed Crystal of Copper Sulphate and Ammonium Monofluophosphate.—Pure copper sulphate and ammonium monofluophosphate were mixed in the molecule proportion (1 : 1), dissolved in the least quantity of water and allowed to crystallise in a vacuum desiccator. In a few hours the solution became turbid owing to the separation of copper fluoride. The solution became turbid again and again and each time it was filtered in a new beaker. In two to three days, hydrolysis stopped and at this stage a crystal of the double salt of nickelammonium sulphate was introduced into the liquid. The nucleus was found to grow uniformly. In the mean time a set of crystals was obtained which were washed, dried and analysed.

	Percentage.	Atomic ratio.
Cu	15'36	0'2439
P	6'873	0'2217
SO ₄	26'77	0'2788

Ratio of the metal : ratio of the acid = 2439 : 5005 = 1 : 2'052.

Hence the formula may be written as $\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_4)_2(\text{SO}_4, \text{PO}_3\text{F})_2, 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The Mixed Crystal of Zinc Sulphate and Ammonium Monofluophosphate.—Pure zinc sulphate and ammonium monofluophosphate in the proportion of 1 : 1 molecule were dissolved in the least quantity of water and allowed to crystallise in a vacuum desiccator. Just like copper the solution went on hydrolysing which did not stop for a long time. When the hydrolysis ceased, it gradually turned into a jelly and did not crystallise at all. The crystals were only obtained by the introduction of nuclei of the double salt of nickelammonium sulphate. The nuclei grew uniformly in the liquid. The nuclei were then taken out and the zinc salt thus obtained was broken up to remove the nuclei and then analysed.

	Zn.	SO ₄ .	P.
Percentage	15'97	26'38	6'703
Atomic ratio	0'2458	0'2748	0'2162

Ratio of the metal : ratio of the acid = 2458 : 4910 = 1 : 1'997.

Hence its formula may be written as $\text{Zn}(\text{NH}_4)_2(\text{SO}_4, \text{PO}_3\text{F})_2, 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The Mixed Crystals of Manganese Sulphate and Ammonium Monofluophosphate.—The salt was prepared by a similar method to that of the zinc salt.

	Mn.	SO ₄ .	P.
Percentage	14'25	27'01	6'896
Atomic ratio	0'2594	0'3157	0'2224

Ratio of the metal : ratio of the acid = 2594 : 5381 = 1 : 2'074.

The formula of the compound should, therefore, be written as $Mn(NH_4)_2(SO_4, PO_3F)_2, 6H_2O$.

Method of Analysis.

Estimation of Copper, Nickel and Cobalt.—Copper, nickel and cobalt were estimated electrolytically after decomposing the compound with concentrated sulphuric acid.

Estimation of Aluminium, Zinc and Manganese.—Aluminium was estimated as phosphate, and zinc and manganese as pyrophosphate after the removal of hydrofluoric acid with concentrated sulphuric acid.

Estimation of Phosphorus.—The compound was first decomposed with nitric and hydrochloric acids on the water-bath; it was evaporated to dryness two to three times after which it was extracted with water and phosphorus was precipitated as ammonium phosphomolybdate. It was then dissolved in ammonia, phosphorus precipitated with magnesia mixture and ignited and weighed as $Mg_2P_2O_7$.

Estimation of Sulphates.—The compound was decomposed with concentrated nitric acid. Nitric acid was then removed by evaporation with concentrated hydrochloric acid for several times on the water-bath. It was then extracted with water and precipitated with barium chloride solution and weighed as $BaSO_4$.

Estimation of Fluorine.—The compound was fused with sodium carbonate, extracted with water and neutralised with nitric acid. It was then made slightly alkaline with caustic soda and silver nitrate was added to it. Ag_3PO_4 formed was removed by filtration and sodium chloride was added to remove the excess of silver ion. The solution was filtered and fluorine was estimated according to the method of Stark and Thorin (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1912, 81, 14).

Estimation of water of crystallisation.—Water of crystallisation was determined according to Jannasch and Penfield's method. In simple salts the weight of water gave the water of crystallisation, whereas in case of double salts with ammonium salt, the total water obtained minus the weight of water corresponding to the hydrogen of ammonium gave the actual weight of water of crystallisation.

My best thanks are due to Dr. P. B. Sarkar for suggesting the problem and to Sir P. C. Rây for his kind encouragement.